

BIOPOLE Newsletter

Spring 2023

compiled by Ruta Hamilton (BAS)

Welcome to our seasonal newsletter!

We find ourselves now in a position where a lot of planning has been done and preparations are being made for upcoming fieldwork, particularly regarding Ny Alesund (Alanna Grant & Nathan Callaghan, UKCEH) and the Chukchi Sea (Stuart Painter, NOC) this summer. BIOPOLE scientists are also taking advantage of some further opportunities, such as a cruise to the Arctic on board R/V Polarstern (Jen Freer & Katrin Linse, BAS).

Furthermore, we have already made the most of some opportunities and already achieved notable successes in the field, such as the deployment of the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean mooring during the recent Polar Trials Cruise on board the RRS Sir David Attenborough and in obtaining opportunistic samples and data during a Southern Ocean cruise aboard RRS Discovery (DY158), including a circumnavigation of the largest moving iceberg presently in the Southern Ocean (A-76a).

Please read on to find out more on these activities as well as the recent

successful Annual Science Meeting at University of Northumbria, Newcastle upon Tyne.

Geraint Tarling (Principal Investigator)

BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting 2023

Between March 1st and 3rd, the BIOPOLE community gathered for the Annual Science Meeting at Northumbria University in Newcastle upon Tyne. The meeting was attended in-person by 25 BIOPOLERS with over 30 participating online. We were also joined online by many members of the Programme Advisory Board. Dr. Anton de Putte travelled from Belgium to join us in Newcastle to represent UN Southern Ocean Decade.

The programme was filled with a combination of progress talks, keynote talks, break-out groups and discussions, all sandwiched between poster sessions. First off, there was a summary of progress made in each of the three main science workpackages by Work-package leaders Bryan Spears and Kate Hendry (WP1), Jen Freer and Stuart Painter (WP2) and Adrian Martin and Andrew Meijers (WP3). Sarah Coombs provided an overview of the project management workpackage (WP4). Thomas Mock delivered the first of two fantastic keynote talks on the molecular work carried out as part of the multinational Arctic programme MOSAiC. The second keynote was by Lee Cooper on the multidisciplinary ocean sampling programme being carried out in the Chukchi Sea.

Quick-fire talks were provided by Elena Garcia-Martin (Arctic fieldwork coordination), Kate Hendry (BIOPOLE cookbook), Nadine Johnston (Stakeholders and outreach), Clara Manno (BIOPOLE mooring), Dave Munday (Idealised modelling), Stefanie Rynders (Arctic modelling), Alanna Grant & Nathan Callaghan (Ny Alesund fieldwork), Petra ten Hoopen (BIOPOLE data management) and Andrew Meijers (BIOPOLE Southern Ocean cruise 1).

We were also grateful for some really informative talks by our stakeholders: Southern Ocean Decade, represented by Anton Van de Putte; and IMBeR, represented by John Claydon. Karen Heywood brought us up to date with progress in PICCOLO, which has a number of synergies with BIOPOLE and will operate close by in the Southern Ocean in the coming season.

Break-out groups considered a number of key themes within BIOPOLE including:

(i) carbon flux and life-cycles, (ii) molecular approaches; (iii) connections between different models and modelling approaches; (iv) connections between models and observations; (v) fieldwork planning and (vi) outreach and impacts.

There were some highly informative posters from Amy Swiggs (Exploring Arctic Sea Ice Thickness Retrievals from Satellite Altimeters); Andrew Yool & Adrian Martin (BIOPOLE, MEDUSA & The Lipid Pump); Anne Braakmann-Folgmann (Melting of giant Antarctic icebergs observed from space); Chelsey Baker (Testing the Implications of Using Lower Temporal Resolution Velocity Component Means for Lagrangian Simulations); Jen Freer (Can *Calanus finmarchicus* succeed in the Arctic? Evidence from project DIAPOD) and Stefanie Rynders & Yevgeny Aksenov (Arctic coastal permafrost erosion).

Other events included an Early Career Research breakfast informed by which Amy Swiggs provided conference with perspectives from ECR community, including a request to the BIOPOLE community to offer mentoring to ECR members.

Those who attended in person enjoyed the many delights that Newcastle had to offer, including an amazing meal at The Botanist, which has its very own tree growing right through the building.

It was a highly productive meeting and an important staging post from which both to reflect on the progress made so far and to look forward to the important work we have ahead of us.

Text written by [Geraint Tarling](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#)

Attendees of the 2023 BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting,
University of Northumbria

Amy Swiggs talking to ECRs from Northumbria University during a poster session

The ASM was hosted in the elegant Great Hall of the Sutherland Building,
University of Northumbria

News from the DY158 Cruise 2022/23

The RRS Discovery cruise DY158, during the austral summer (20 Dec 2022 - 30 Jan 2023, Figure 1a-d) was a British Antarctic Survey core science cruise carried out in the Atlantic sector of the Southern Ocean. Its principal task was to carry out oceanographic transects, bioacoustics surveys and scientific mooring retrievals and redeployments in order to maintain valuable time-series data on the physics, biogeochemistry and biology of this Southern Ocean sector. However, in travelling through so many regions of mutual interest to BIOPOLE, it also provided a fantastic platform to undertake some opportunistic BIOPOLE work.

The cruise was conducted by the British Antarctic Survey's Ecosystems and Polar Oceans Teams and was led by Ryan Saunders as Principal Scientific Officer. It was focussed on the Scotia Sea and Weddell Sea regions of the Southern Ocean and included eight BIOPOLE scientists: Povl Abrahamsen, Nadine Johnston, Clara Manno, Mike Meredith, Ryan Saunders, Gabi Stowasser, Geraint Tarling, and PhD candidate Laura Taylor. They were part of a larger team of 'Disco scientists' and were supported by the wonderful NOC technical team and RRS Discovery officers and crew.

With all hands on deck, Povl and Mike led the physical oceanography effort and oversaw the deployment of numerous CTDs to collect oceanographic data and water samples across the entire survey region (Figure 2a-c), which is of use to BIOPOLE workpackage 1 (WP1). The water collected by the CTDs was further sampled by Laura, Clara, and Gabi for biogeochemical and phytoplankton analyses, highly relevant to both WP1 and WP2. Nadine and Geraint led the collection of copepod samples using Bongo nets (Figure 2a-c). Some individual copepods (species *Calanoides acutus*) were directly preserved to determine their body condition and metabolic rate (via biochemical proxies). Other individual copepods were used in on-board experiments to measure their respiration rate at a range of temperatures (Figure 3a-e). These data will be used by BIOPOLE to calculate the contribution of this species to the 'lipid pump' (WP2), and hence better parameterise the carbon cycle within the NEMO-MEDUSA Earth System model (under WP3).

The real bonus for BIOPOLE in making these opportunistic collections is that it adds an austral summer seasonal time point to the austral spring and autumn time-points planned for dedicated BIOPOLE cruises SO1 (Nov-Dec 2023) and SO2 (Feb-Mar 2025) respectively.

As a further bonus to WP1, BIOPOLE scientists made full use of a circumnavigation of the enormous megaberg A-76a to collect physical and biogeochemical samples (see Povl Abrahamsen's article).

We even got to see the RRS Sir David Attenborough when we disembarked at the Falkland Islands (Figure 1a-d). Altogether a highly successful opportunistic BIOPOLE cruise!

Text written by [Nadine Johnston](#), [Geraint Tarling](#), [Ryan Saunders](#), and [Povl Abrahamsen](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#), photo credits - [Povl Abrahamsen](#), [Mike Meredith](#), [Sarah Manthorpe](#), [Geraint Tarling](#), and [Nadine Johnston](#) ([British Antarctic Survey](#))

Figure 1a. We met RRS Discovery in Montevideo on Dec 20th 2022

Figure 1b. The cruise track took us first to South Georgia and then along transect A23 into the ice in the Weddell Sea and then back towards the South Orkney Islands before heading to the Falkland Islands to disembark

Figure 1c. Science party of cruise DY158

Figure 1d. RRS Discovery alongside RRS Sir David Attenborough in Mare Harbour, Falkland Islands, Jan 30th 2023

Figure 2a. Deployment of a CTD (RRS Discovery, DY158, Dec 2022 – Jan 2023)

Figure 2b. Preparing to deploy a Bongo net
(RRS Discovery, DY158, Dec 2022 – Jan 2023)

Figure 2c. Deploying a Bongo net (RRS Discovery, DY158, Dec 2022 – Jan 2023)

Figure 3a. Nadine Johnston preparing microplates to measure copepod respiration

Figure 3b. A microplate respirometer containing copepods (*Calanoides acutus* stage CV)

Figure 3c. Microplate respirometers were incubated in parallel at three different temperatures through housing in separate temperature regulated scientific fridges

Figure 3d. Copepod *Calanoides acutus* (stage CV) showing a large internal lipid sac (total body length ~5 mm)

Figure 3e. Magnified view of a copepod in a microplate cell

BIOPOLE Encounters “Megaberg” A-76a

At the end of cruise DY158 on RRS Discovery, scientists from BIOPOLE had a unique opportunity to study one of the largest icebergs on earth, iceberg A-76a. The iceberg calved from the western edge of Ronne Ice Shelf in the southern Weddell Sea in May 2021. After gradually drifting north along the shelf break in the western Weddell Sea, the iceberg reached open water in late 2022, but then appeared to stop northwest of the South Orkney Islands, spinning almost on the spot from early November 2022 until late January 2023.

On 25-26 Jan 2023 RRS Discovery made a full lap of the iceberg, which at this time measured around 135 x 25 km, with a freeboard of up to 50 m high in places. Scientists collected water samples from the ship's pumped uncontaminated seawater system, which will be analysed for nutrients, oxygen and silica isotopes, phytoplankton, and more! This opportunistic sampling will show how large Antarctic icebergs affect the physical and chemical properties of the ocean and the ecosystems that they pass through as they melt. They are of particular relevance to tasks 1.1 (nutrients and tracers) and 1.2 (source to sea processes), supplementing the planned sampling on the upcoming BIOPOLE cruises on RRS Sir David Attenborough and land-based campaigns at Rothera and KEP.

The iceberg continued its northward drift shortly after RRS *Discovery* left, initially heading toward Shag Rocks, and now drifting east toward South Georgia. BAS will continue to monitor its trajectory over the coming months.

More information about iceberg A-76a can be found at <https://www.bas.ac.uk/media-post/first-ever-pictures-of-giant-iceberg-from-antarcticas-brunt-ice-shelf/>.

Text written by [Povl Abrahamsen](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#)

Iceberg A-76a continues as far as the eye can see. Photo: Chris Auckland, BAS

The textures on the side of iceberg A-76a show how it is made up of years of accumulating snowfall, and how waves are now eroding the ice near the water line,

causing large blocks to break off and fall into the ocean. Photo: Povl Abrahamsen, BAS

Animation showing the track of RRS Discovery during its circumnavigation of iceberg A-76a on 25-26 Jan 2023, with collection of water samples from the ship's uncontaminated seawater supply. Background satellite image from NOAA-20 VIIRS, downloaded through NASA WorldView. Credit: Povl Abrahamsen, BAS

Feature on Enma Elena Garcia Strategic Lead for Arctic Fieldwork

Elena: 'I'm a biogeochemist working within the Ocean BioGeoscience group at the National Oceanography Centre in Southampton. During the last decade I've been investigating the role of phytoplankton, zooplankton and bacteria on the marine carbon cycling, the coupling between oxygen production (primary production) and consumption (plankton respiration) processes and the influence of the community structure and environmental variables, such as temperature and dissolved organic matter, on the plankton metabolism. In BIOPOLE I wear two different hats:

a) I am part of the WP2 which focusses on the biological processes that modify the carbon to nutrient ratios in polar environments. Specifically, I run laboratory experiments with different cultured phytoplankton to determine the direct and indirect effects of warming and nutrient supply on microplankton cell size, metabolism (primary production and respiration) and biomass stoichiometry. Our results will allow to understand better the responses of polar phytoplankton to changing climatic conditions.

b) I am also the Strategic Lead for Arctic Fieldwork, and when I wear this hat, I serve as a point of contact between BIOPOLE researchers and BIOPOLE project partners, facilitating the interactions between them and coordinating the activities, to ensure that BIOPOLE maximize the resources available in the Arctic.

I was lucky to live a year in Tromsø (Norway) many many years ago, where I spent hours looking at polar plankton under the microscope. BIOPOLE has given me the opportunity to spend more time with these cold, beautiful creatures without the need of woolly hat and gloves.

I have green fingers, not only for phytoplankton, and I like growing my own veggies. Ohh, I love how tasty they are!!!'

[Enma Elena Garcia-Martin](#) from the [National Oceanography Centre](#)

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BIOPOLE Mooring Deployment on Polar Science Trials (SD025)

One of the main aims of BIOPOLE is to consider the amount of carbon exported by polar ecosystems into deep ocean layers. In the Southern Ocean, our strategy is to deploy a biophysical mooring within the Marginal Ice Zone where there is a large amount of surface productivity that can potentially be exported. We identified a region in the Powell Basin, between the Antarctic Peninsula and the South Orkney Islands, where the combination of ice, physical oceanography and rich plankton communities made it an ideal site in which to measure the rate of this carbon export.

Fortuitously, we were able to take advantage of the visit of the RRS Sir David Attenborough (RRS SDA) to this site as part of its Polar Science Trials in February and March this year. We prepared a mooring with a number of sensors to measure the salinity, temperature and oxygen content of the water as well as the direction and velocity of prevailing currents. Of particular importance in terms of measuring carbon export are two sediment traps (one at 600 m, the other at 2800 m) that capture the downward rain of particulate matter resulting from a combination of the retreat of sea-ice, the collapse of phytoplankton blooms and the waste generated by zooplankton. We are hopeful that the 600 m trap may also catch copepods during their seasonal descent to deeper ocean layers. These seasonally-descending copepods generate much carbon export through a process called the 'lipid pump'.

The Polar Science Trials team worked hard to ready the instruments and mooring hardware for deployment during the cruise. It was successfully deployed on the 2nd March 2023 at 16:27 at 62° 08.534' S 50° 31.150' W in 3400 m of water. The mooring will stay in place collecting data and samples for approximately 2 years, at which point it is planned to be recovered by the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean 2 cruise.

Text written by [Sophie Fielding](#), [Clara Manno](#), [Sally Thorpe](#) and [Geraint Tarling](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#)

Site of the BIOPOLE mooring in the Powell Basin showing the bathymetry

The velocity of prevailing currents at ~2500 m depth from a high resolution regional sea ice-ocean model (courtesy of Emma Young)

Biopole mooring 2023 (3400 m water depth)

Set up of the BIOPOLE mooring, showing the array of instruments secured along its mooring line. The surface buoy rests at a depth of 200 m to minimise the impact of passing icebergs. The array is moored to the seabed by heavy chain. Acoustically-enabled release mechanisms are positioned just above the chain which open their jaws on receiving an encoded signal, detaching them from the chain and allowing the entire array to float to the surface to be recovered

Deployment of surface buoy that keeps the mooring upright and also houses oceanographic instruments and the beacons that enable the mooring to be relocated for retrieval (RRS SDA, Powell Basin, March 2023)

Deployment of sediment trap that will capture sinking particulate matter and, potentially, descending copepods (RRS SDA, Powell Basin, 2023)

Deployment of chain that will hold the mooring in place (RRS SDA, Powell Basin, March 2023)

BIOPOLE Cookbook

The BIOPOLE Cookbook has been released on the [BIOPOLE website](#) and is available to the environmental sciences community. As it sounds, the Cookbook provides a list of ‘recipes’ for sampling and preservation of samples in the field. The document also contains the basics of how and where the samples will be analysed.

Water and sediment samples will be collected throughout the BIOPOLE project from both terrestrial and marine stations. The observational data from the sample analyses will form important deliverables of work packages WP1 and WP2, and – together with existing archived data – will feed more widely into the modelling aspects of WP3. In other words, these samples will form the scientific backbone of a significant proportion of BIOPOLE and will be essential for addressing most of the underlying research questions. Land-based work will involve the collection of samples by foot and small boats, whereas larger-scale ocean-going expeditions will involve sampling using Niskin bottles attached to CTD rosette frames (most recently during the Polar Science Trials on the RRS Sir David Attenborough).

The aim of the Cookbook is to standardise methodology, to ensure that the sampling and analyses are well documented and reproducible. This is particularly important for BIOPOLE given the number of different organisations involved within the team, and because we will be working with partner organisations and stakeholders – particularly in the Arctic satellite stations – to improve the spatial and temporal coverage of our sampling.

Such Cookbooks are not a new idea and have been used more widely in the scientific community before. Other documents that might be useful to the BIOPOLE team include the [GEOTRACES Cookbook](#), [Go-SHIP](#) documentation, and the [Nansen Legacy](#) sampling guide. These documents are also all available on the BIOPOLE Sharepoint site.

The BIOPOLE Cookbook deliverable was led by Kate Hendry (BAS), but with a lot of valuable input from Dan Mayor and the NERC LOCATE team, Ed Mawji

(NOC), and Amy Pickard, Alanna Grant, Chris Barry, Steve Lofts and Nathan Callaghan (UK CEH).

Text written by [Kate Hendry](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#), photo credits - [Sophie Fielding](#) ([British Antarctic Survey](#)) and [Isabel Seguro](#) ([University of East Anglia](#))

Deploying the CTD rosette on board the RRS Sir David Attenborough

Sampling from Niskin bottles around the rosette

Sampling from Niskin bottles around the rosette

Upcoming Relevant Meetings

IMBeR ECR initiative with IMECaN representation

IMBeR ClimEco8 Summer School – Sustaining the Ocean We Need for the Future We Want

Deadline for applications is 10 April 2023

For more information about the summer school and to apply to be considered as a participant, [please click here](#)

**2023 Ecosystem Studies of the Subarctic and Arctic Seas (ESSAS) Annual Science Meeting:
“Ecological, social and economic dynamics of high-latitude coastal systems”**

20-22 June 2023, Institute of Marine Research (IMR) in Bergen, Norway

Deadline for abstract submissions is 31 March 2023

[Note: BIOPOLE has submitted an abstract on programme objectives and impacts]

For more information about the meeting and to register, [please click here](#)

SOOS Symposium

SOUTHERN OCEAN IN A CHANGING WORLD

**The first Southern Ocean Observing System
(SOOS) Symposium**

14-18 August 2023 in Hobart, Tasmania

Register by 30 April 2023

[Note: BIOPOLE will submit an abstract on programme objectives and impacts]

**For more information about the symposium and to
register, [please click here](#)**

